

Bridging Data and AIOps for Future AI Advancements with Human-in-the-loop.

The AI-DAPT Concept

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Abstract— The transition of artificial intelligence (AI) from research to deployment has underscored the critical importance of leveraging data effectively in developing and evaluating AI models. Despite their pivotal role in determining performance, fairness, and robustness, data are often undervalued in AI research, lacking a data-centric focus. In response, the AI-DAPT project pioneers a data-centric approach that aligns with AI methodologies to address the pressing need for reliable and trustworthy AI systems. This paper presents the AI-DAPT project and concept, highlighting its innovative solutions. Through advanced techniques like synthetic data generation and hybrid science-guided Machine Learning (ML), AI-DAPT aims to mitigate vulnerabilities in conventional AI paradigms. The developed solutions will be demonstrated in healthcare, robotics, energy, and manufacturing scenarios, hence navigating real-world complexities.

Keywords—AI pipelines, Data pipelines, Data for AI, Hybrid Science-Guided AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has paved a long way since its inception and is now widely adopted across various industries, shaping our world in ways that were once thought impossible, and impacting various aspects of society, economy, and governance. From personalized healthcare interventions to optimizing energy consumption in smart cities, as AI transitions from research to deployment, leveraging the appropriate data to develop and evaluate AI models has evolved into one of its greatest challenges [1]. Data are the fundamental asset driving today's AI progress, generating unprecedented insights, enabling evidence-based decision-making, and delivering tangible business and economic benefits and innovation to all stakeholders.

Despite their essential role in shaping the performance, fairness, and robustness of AI systems, data are paradoxically undervalued and often overlooked. Current AI research typically lacks a data-centric focus, neglecting the fundamental importance of data in driving AI advancements. [2]. We can identify several key bottlenecks that prevent the realization of such a focus:

- Poor data planning and scoping are common issues, often leading to delays in obtaining vital data, which frequently needs to be sourced from various departments within the organization.
- Data may come in different formats, suffer from the so-called downtime effect (partial/corrupted data), and miss semantic information.
- Data scientists spend significant time redeveloping the same features across different solutions.
- Representative data in terms of fairness, coverage, etc that are appropriate for AI may be hard to access.
- Although synthetic data are expected to overtake actual data in training AI models, their flexible nature may render it biased in behaviour or inconsistent/inaccurate in comparison to reality.
- Data drift: the performance of deployed AI models appears to be degrading, making less accurate predictions or generally providing different inference results than what the models were expected to.
- The insights gained through data/AI observability are not yet actionable enough to automatically trigger appropriate remedy actions, such as retraining models at the most opportune moments.
- Most explainable AI (XAI) approaches typically focus on the data scientist's attempt to explain the

inner workings of a specific black-box model [3], and their results are not suitable for consumption by non-technical users.

Lastly, AI is not intended to replace or undermine science-based knowledge and well-established models, such as physics-based models or optimization algorithms. Instead, AI can complement these traditional approaches. The synergy between data-driven AI models and science-based first-principles models remains largely unexplored in the current research landscape, presenting a significant opportunity for innovative advancements [4].

The AI-DAPT project (<https://www.ai-dapt.eu>) is a HORIZON Research and Innovation Action (Grant Agreement n° 101135826). Its main objective is to provide an AI-Ops framework for automated, intelligent and reliable operations to support the lifecycle of data/AI pipelines, enforcing the humans-in-the-loop aspect and the coupling of hybrid science-guided and AI Models. This paper gives a general overview of the AI-DAPT contributions, main concepts and technical architecture.

A. AI-DAPT Overview

AI-DAPT brings forward a data-centric mentality in AI, that is effectively fused with a model-centric, science-based approach, across the complete lifecycle of AI-Ops, by introducing end-to-end automation that is supported by AI-based techniques, across the design, the execution, the observability and the constant optimisation of intelligent data/AI pipelines.

As the demand for real, high-quality data intensifies to unlock the untapped potential of AI, AI-DAPT aims to significantly contribute to current research and advance state-of-the-art techniques. This includes sophisticated XAI-driven data operations, covering mining, exploration, documentation, valuation, interoperability, annotation, cleaning, augmentation, and bias detection. Additionally, AI-DAPT will focus on collaborative feature engineering to optimize data usage, the development of hybrid science-guided and AI-based models, sparse model generation, and adaptive AI for model retraining purposes. The project will establish the underlying methodological and technical foundations across different axes that will complementarily and interactively work together as follows.

1) AI/Data Axis

AI-DAPT shall adopt novel automated approaches, fused with targeted human-in-the-loop aspects, to improve “data for AI” pipelines in a systematic and scalable way. Typical data management activities including (but not limited to) data definition, preparation, annotation, cleaning, manipulation, synthetic generation and observability will be revamped through AI-driven automation. This approach leverages XAI techniques to ensure human interaction and informed intervention when needed. It allows for final decision-making regarding pipeline configuration and ensures the quality of the data and the ethical use of AI. Through the AI-DAPT data-centric AI research, the raw datasets will be revamped into appropriate, added value, up-to-date and reusable features, that effectively reduce the “time to insights”.

2) AI/Model Axis

AI-DAPT shall explore and promote hybrid science-AI solutions, bringing together data-driven AI models and science-based first-principles models, that build on high-

quality and reliable data. AI-DAPT introduces precise automation interventions throughout the AI model lifecycle, encompassing building, training, validation, and observability stages. This approach facilitates continuous and dynamic enhancements to AI systems by significantly reducing the “time to detection” and “time to resolution” for any issues within the AI pipeline. It enables training on-the-fly and ensures adaptability and reliability of AI solutions across a spectrum of production environments and settings.

In order to demonstrate the actual innovation and added value resulting from the scientific advancements of AI-DAPT, validation will be carried out in two closely linked aspects:

- Through their actual application to address real-life problems in four (4) representative industries that are characterized by a varying degree of AI maturity: (a) Health, (b) Robotics, (c) Energy, and (d) Manufacturing.
- Through their integration in different AI solutions, either open source (e.g. Jupyter, Acumos AI) or commercial (S5 Enterprise Analytics Suite, Qlik, etc.). The purpose of such an integration is to demonstrate that the AI-DAPT results bring added value within the established AI market landscape.

II. BACKGROUND AND CURRENT LANDSCAPE

The AI-DAPT project aims at pushing the boundaries and advancing the state-of-the-art of two research areas: (1) Data pipelines for robust and trustworthy AI, including data management & Synthetic data generation, and (2) AI pipelines, including Hybrid science-ML, Efficient AI-Ops, and Adaptive AI. The current status of scientific and industrial solutions in these topics is outlined next, along with the innovative contributions anticipated.

A. Data pipelines for robust and trustworthy AI, including data management & synthetic data generation

As the amount of data continues to grow, data pipelines have become increasingly critical in modern data architectures and AI systems [5]. Effective pipelines rely on data management, utilising key technologies for data design (i.e., data sourcing and documentation), data sculpting (selection, cleaning, annotation) and data strategies for model testing, monitoring, and optimisation. However, generating high-quality datasets for reliable AI models still remains challenging due to the high cost and effort involved in data curation and annotation [6].

Hence, data is a critical component in the development and deployment of AI systems. In this direction, Data harvesting provides the foundations for effective downstream data processing and analysis. Automated data ingestion techniques for AI pipelines have experienced major advancements, such as data virtualisation allowing data to be accessed and queried without the need for data movement or replication. Further improvements during data harvesting in the data quality can be made through Data fusion which combines data from multiple sources to create more accurate and concise datasets than any individual data source [7].

Exploratory data analysis (EDA) is also crucial in building reliable models, involving data analysis and visualisation to detect patterns, understand data characteristics/distributions and guide data pre-processing for model training. Recent EDA advancements use Machine Learning (ML)-based methods for automated process of data analysis and visualization (through

model training and insights generation). Explainable AI (XAI) also enables transparency and interpretation in AI models, providing users with interactive visualisation and immersive interfaces enabling data exploration and manipulation [8]. Another critical process is Data Valuation, focusing on assessing the significance of various data types, eliminating low-quality or biased data that may negatively impact the performance of the AI model [9]. Data Shapley scores and influence approximation methods showed promising results in computing data valuation for large AI models [10], while another approach utilised prediction uncertainty to detect and remove low-quality data points, proving an alternative way to filter out data that may harm the model's performance [11].

When the objective is to identify the right data that can enhance the model's accuracy and generalization, Data Selection can play a vital role as it selects the most relevant and informative subset of data to train the model, while reducing training time and computational resources. Common techniques include sampling (randomly selecting a subset of the data); feature selection (focusing on selecting the most relevant features or variables); instance selection (choosing the most representative instances from the entire dataset); and active learning (iteratively selecting the most informative instances for annotation to improve the model's performance). Recent methods focus also on deep learning (DL)-based methods which automatically select the most informative and representative data, involving training neural networks (NNs) to learn the patterns and structure of the data, and use them to select the most relevant/ informative data [12].

Data cleaning is a crucial step in developing robust and accurate AI models and involves identifying and correcting errors, inconsistencies, and missing values in the data. Popular data cleaning approaches include statistical methods analysing data distribution for anomalies/outliers detection; rule-based methods that use pre-defined rules for detecting-correction data errors; ML-based methods that use algorithms to learn from data and automatically identify and correct errors; recently also data cleaning DL-based methods have also been developed, training neural networks to learn the patterns and structure of the data and use them to detect/ correct errors [13].

Data Augmentation has emerged as the most effective ML method, able to increase the amount/ diversity of training data by creating new examples from existing ones, thereby enhancing AI model's robustness and generalisation, which is crucial when dealing with limited/ imbalanced datasets. These techniques can be applied to various types of data and is considered of great importance in computer vision [14]. A new element gaining prominence in data pipelines is Synthetic data generation, referring to the process of generating new data that share same statistical properties as an original dataset, while not containing any actual information from the original data. Synthetic data became an important game changer in various data-rich domains/ tasks, ultimately enabling researchers, software developers/engineers to generate larger datasets that would not even be available using real data [15]. Thanks to advancements in simulations and generative models, synthetic data became a vital alternative to real-world data for training models, while their competitive advantages are being showcased in cases of limited or biased real-world data, when it is too expensive/impractical to collect more data (e.g. computer vision, natural language processing (NLP), text-to-speech) [16], or when sensitive/confidential data (e.g., clinical/healthcare [17], business data) cannot be shared due to

privacy implications/regulations (e.g. GDPR). Advanced techniques for generating synthetic data include methods such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) promising in image/speech synthesis and text generation applications, Variational Autoencoders (VAEs)[18], DCGAN, CycleGAN[19], and data augmentation; However, synthetic data presents challenges related to data quality, lack of evaluation metrics for assessing generalisability and trustworthiness, and potential bias (inherited from pre-processing, collection, and algorithms[20]). Data utility assessment evaluates the quality and relevance of data for a specific AI application by measuring if it meets the requirements of the model and identifying any issues/ biases impacting the model's performance. Research in data utility assessment uses data valuation techniques like Shapley scores and influence approximation to identify valuable data and optimise data collection strategies.

Innovation introduced: AI-DAPT will utilise a human-AI teaming approach, where AI/ML is used to identify, suggest and perform data operations, and humans are informed in a comprehensive manner and act as the final validators of those actions. Automated data harvesting techniques will ensure ingestion of raw data that gradually becomes suitable for sharing and use in ML/AI applications, upon undergoing the processing imposed by the AI-based data documentation, remediation, and augmentation steps, as well as their associated metadata curation, data cleaning and quality augmentation, semantic inference, enhancing consequently all aspects of FAIRness in data. Also, AI-DAPT will practically put into use sophisticated techniques and Explainable AI methods during the lifecycle of data pipelines in order to improve the training datasets and deliver more trustworthy AI solutions to business problems.

To enhance the representativeness and suitability of training data for AI solutions, AI-DAPT will create decision-based data valuation algorithms. These algorithms will identify quality metrics, including bias, and leverage synthetic data generation techniques to supplement or substitute real data. This approach aims to enhance AI models, safeguard sensitive information, and address issues related to bias and data imbalance. Finally, AI-DAPT's automated data "observability" services will utilise self-adjusting ML/AI methods to timely detect and address data downtime and drift, while ensuring continuous improvement through tailored patterns and rules that are prompted by the relevant evaluation and any necessary corrections proposed.

B. AI pipelines including Hybrid science-ML, Efficient AI-Ops, and Adaptive AI

A growing interest has been noted in recent years in AI/ML pipelines (i.e., the end-to-end process of developing and deploying AI models) to support training, evaluating and validating more accurate, interpretable and adaptable models.

Recent advancements in AI models introduced alternative approaches to improve model's accuracy and interpretability, such as the Hybrid science-ML or science-guided machine learning (SGML), integrating science-based models from diverse scientific disciplines (e.g., biology, chemistry, etc.), with ML models to solve complex problems, enhance output accuracy, interpretability, advance data analysis, prediction and decision-making [21], [22].

Model training is another fundamental ML process in building accurate models, where advancements in federated

learning also enable training of ML models on decentralized data; particularly useful in scenarios where data privacy and security are critical [23]. Another trending breakthrough is the development of GPT-4 (Generative Pre-trained Transformer 4) language model by OpenAI (<https://openai.com>), demonstrating how deep learning models can be pre-trained on a vast dataset using unsupervised learning to acquire valuable data representations, which can be further optimized for specific tasks with supervised learning techniques.

Model Ablation and evaluation techniques can prevent models from relying on shortcuts through misleading correlations in training data. They involve testing AI models on modified inputs to reveal any spurious correlations. In this direction, Multi-accuracy auditing identifies subgroups where the AI model performs poorly by training an auditor algorithm to predict and cluster errors using metadata. This provides interpretable insights into the reasons and locations for the AI model's mistakes [24]. Sparse modelling can also help in building reliable AI models with less data and time/energy/data storage requirements, by extracting the necessary parts from given data and suiting limited data cases or explainability needs and capturing essential data features with minimal coefficients, thus improving data analysis and processing efficiency. Sparse modelling is well-established into a wide range of AI/ML applications, particular in machine vision systems and in signal processing [25].

The last process of making trained models available for use in production environments (integrated into various applications/ systems) is typically referred as the Model deployment. This process encompasses multiple steps, including testing the model's performance, packaging it into a deployable format, and then deploying it for operational use. Significant advances in AI model deployment techniques include containerization for efficient and scalable models' deployment, and Serverless Computing, because of the flexibility offered to scale up or down based on the demand and reduce costs [26].

Monitoring and analysis of model's behaviour can be achieved through Data Model Observability, with advancements including the introduction of the Google's "What-If Tool" (<https://pair-code.github.io/what-if-tool/>) enabling ML models performance visualisation, allowing data scientists/engineers to observe inputs' impact on predictions via features, such as input and output data visualization, performance metrics, fairness analysis. Furthermore, XAI offers interpretable explanations of a model's decision-making process, aiding in the identification and diagnosis of problems through various methods such as local explanation, explanation by example, text explanation, visual explanation, feature relevance, model simplification, transparent model for Machine Learning (ML), explanation of deep network processing and DL representation, explanation of producing systems, and hybrid transparent and black-box methods for DL. Model agnostic methods (e.g., feature effect [27]), can be applied to all black-box models. In contrast, model-specific methods, such as saliency maps for Deep NN are explicitly tailored for particular ML algorithms. Local methods, such as LIME and counterfactual explanations explain individual predictions, whereas global methods, such as ALE plots opt for a global understanding of the model [28]. Finally, surrogate models are external interpretable components designed to mimic the black-box model behaviour [29]. Several XAI solutions have been implemented in open-source libraries to

varying levels of maturity. A range of these libraries provide implementations of individual methods (e.g., LIME or SHAP - github.com/marcotcr/lime, github.com/slundberg/shap).

Further optimisation of operational AI models in production environments can be achieved through Drift Monitoring, detecting and monitoring changes in the distribution of data used by a ML model; this is crucial because data distribution changes can reduce model accuracy, causing errors and poor performance. Breakthroughs in drift monitoring include: i) statistical process control methods, such as Drift Detection Method; ii) hypothesis testing, such as Adaptive Windowing [30] and iii) distance-based methods such as Kernel Change Detection, effective in detecting changes in the data distribution when the data is high-dimensional or non-linear [31].

Adaptive learning also assists in AI models optimisation by continuous adjustments of their learning process (learning rate adaptation, dynamic architectures, data selection, transfer learning) based on feedback from the data/environment, which enhances accuracy, speed, performance, and reduces training resources. Recent advancements include the use of meta-reinforcement learning to optimise learning process [32], the development of adaptive algorithms that can learn from non-stationary data and the integration of adaptive learning techniques into deep learning frameworks [33].

Innovation introduced: AI-DAPT will bring together two, till recently disparate worlds, the science-based knowledge and modelling, e.g., physics-based models or optimization algorithms, and AI through different tight and loose coupling options. Also, it will introduce an integrated framework and automated AI model delivery and optimisation services integrating hybrid-science models, towards more accurate and scientifically consistent predictions. Introducing human-in-the-loop (HITL) approaches teaming with ML (where feasible), will improve AI model's optimisation thus aligning with EC's Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI [34], where human agency and oversight is among the key requirements of trustworthy AI.

AI-DAPT will employ AutoML to support the configuration and training of appropriate ML/DL models. Model deployment will be supported by novel MLOps approaches enabling efficient and reliable model deployment, while optimising resources consumption. Once in production, AI-DAPT will offer model observability at the core of model health in terms of model and feature drift detection, input and output data quality, model performance, and explainability of root-causes and recommended actions. Finally, AI-DAPT will also focus its efforts in deciding the optimal moment to automatically trigger for retraining a hybrid model and deploying it, without intruding the overall AI pipeline that may be already available in production settings.

III. THE AI-DAPT CONCEPT AND TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE

AI-DAPT aims at reinstating the pure data-related work in its rightful place in AI and at reinforcing the generalizability, reliability, trustworthiness and fairness of AI solutions. AI-DAPT brings forward a data-centric mentality in AI, that is effectively fused with a model-centric, science-based approach, across the complete lifecycle of AI-Ops, by introducing end-to-end automation that is supported by AI-based techniques, across the design, the execution, the observability and the constant optimisation of intelligent data/AI pipelines.

Fig. 1. AI-DAPT Concept of data-AI pipelines across their lifecycle

A. The AI-DAPT Concept

1) AI-DAPT Phase I “Data Design for AI”

A data scientist starts identifying data that are appropriate for the AI solution (“Data for AI Purposing” step) from the list of datasets that are available in an organization, leveraging the knowledge that domain experts also possess. Based on the appropriate user configuration, an automated process (“Data Mining/Harvesting” step) to fetch the appropriate raw data from the companies’ internal databases and data lakes where they are stored by default, needs to be deployed. Such a process may take place recurrently to ensure that the involved parties can effectively study and use up-to-date data. The data scientists and business users collaboratively analyse the data at hand (“Exploratory Data Analysis” step) to summarize their main qualitative and qualitative characteristics, using summary statistics and data visualization methods, while discussing the various occurrences that appear in the actual values to gain a thorough understanding. As an AI model’s performance is highly dependent on the context of its training and evaluation data, it is important to document the data design context in standardized and transparent reports. To this end, the data need to be catalogued (“Data Documentation” step): (a) at dataset level by extracting a collection of metadata that serves as the available data profile, providing information to evaluate the fitness of the data for its intended uses, complementing quality findings from the “Exploratory Data Analysis” step, defining data privacy and ownership protocols, and enforcing data provenance by tracking its origins and production processes, and (b) at feature level, extracting the relevant features and storing them in the AI-DAPT feature store to facilitate access for the subsequent feature engineering activities. Taking into consideration the fact that the data need to have a good coverage of all scenarios, in terms of both typical cases and edge cases that the AI may encounter in practice, the data need to be assessed (“Data Valuation” step) to evaluate their quality and how fit for purpose they are, and to detect any bias and spurious correlations through decision-based valuation methods.

2) AI-DAPT Phase II “Data Scupltng/Nurturing /Curation for AI”

A data scientist applies AI/ML-based techniques over the data in a systematic manner in order to ensure they are representative, appropriate and of high quality for the AI solution that is under development. To this end, a set of techniques are applied to annotate the data (“Data Annotation” step) in 2 levels: (i) at feature structure level where the features

are semantically annotated through their mapping to a common semantic model of their choice (that may semi-automatically reconcile the underlying data models, ontologies and standards in a specific domain), (ii) at feature value level where new features can be created through automated labelling from an existing or a set of existing features. In the “Data Selection” step, the relevant features for the AI model are extracted and new features are also engineered as the data scientists consider appropriate for their experimentation. In order to handle any incorrect, incomplete, inaccurate, irrelevant or missing parts of the corresponding data, appropriate AI/ML (automated) cleaning techniques need to be configured (under human supervision) and applied (in the “Data Cleaning” step), complementing any user-defined cleaning rules, to increase the data quality and utility.

3) AI-DAPT Phase III “Data Generation for AI”

A data scientist is responsible for addressing the critical problem of the lack of representative data due to privacy limitations, difficulty to access or mere unavailability of appropriate data. In this context, synthetic data can be created (“Synthetic Data Generation” step) to augment or replace real data to improve AI models, protect sensitive data, and mitigate bias and imbalance. Considering the disparity between synthetic data and reality, which often leads to a performance decline when deploying AI models trained on synthetic data into real-world scenarios, the “Data Utility Assessment” step aims to assist data scientists in evaluating whether synthetic data possess a distribution comparable to original data without exacerbating disparities. This is achieved by combining objective and subjective measures of utility and cross-validating various utility metrics.

4) AI-DAPT Phase IV “Model Delivery for AI”

A data scientist handles the lifecycle of the relevant AI model from its development to evaluation and deployment. A key concept in AI-DAPT is the hybrid science-guided ML for industrial settings. Process models and parameter estimation are traditional concepts widely used in industrial plants in several domains (manufacturing, robotics, power plants, biomed etc.). Early modelling methodologies involved complex systems of mathematical differential/algebraic equations (aka first-principles models) to capture process knowledge and domain expertise (i.e., physical and chemical properties, static and dynamic behaviours, causal relationships among observed quantities, etc.) in order to support predictive control, process simulation and operational optimization.

First-principles models are by definition white-box models, since they uncover the process's inner logic and the decision steps involved. On the other hand, the massive amounts of data available from industrial processes in the era of Industry 4.0 has led to an explosion in the development of ML/DL models as an alternative to first-principles models, with many of them being black-box models. Hybrid, science-guided models are a combination of first principles and machine learning models. Therefore, in the “Hybrid Science-ML Model Definition” step, a data scientist may opt for proceeding with: (a) a purely data-driven approach based on selected machine learning or deep learning models for which the hyperparameters (e.g. activations functions, learning rate, pooling size, and hidden layers and units) need to be configured leveraging grid search, random search, and other search algorithms; (b) a science-guided approach based on science-based knowledge and data-based knowledge for an accurate and scientifically consistent prediction, that typically combines a data-based ML model with a science-based first-principles model. Such a combination may range from loose-coupling scenarios, where an ML model can be trained to correct the output of the first-principles model itself, to tight-coupling scenarios, where the ML follows a specific architecture to incorporate pre-existing knowledge that can be provided by a domain expert. An example of the first scenario is to use a first-principles model as data generator and having plant data to measure the residuals, whereas an example of the second scenario is guiding a deep learning model to extract specific health indicators for each patient, before predicting the appropriate medication.

It needs to be noted that the selection, composition, and parameterization of the ML models can be automated, to the extent it is possible, through AutoML[35]. Then, the typical process of training the selected models (“Model Training” step), and evaluating the model performance (“Model Evaluation” step) follows to conclude to a trustworthy, performant and reliant (hybrid) AI model. In preparation for the upcoming “Data-Model optimization” stage, the emphasis for model training, explanation, and evaluation will be on models that take into account uncertainty when making predictions. Incorporating uncertainty in predictions is vital in assessing the reliability of a model and is necessary for monitoring its accuracy, especially under distribution shift. To cater for energy efficiency, a data scientist may also consider the configuration of a sparse model as a way of representing complex data in a more efficient or compact way minimizing the required training data, which can be faster to compute and require less resources (“Sparse Model Generation” step), making them ideal for cases of edge computing scenarios. Following the MLOps principles and approach, the resulting (hybrid) AI model is deployed and maintained in production reliably and efficiently (“Model Deployment” step). From this moment onwards, the AI solution is applied in real-life settings to solve the problem at hand.

5) AI-DAPT Phase V “Data-Model Optimization for AI”

The overall AI solution is continuously monitored and automatically improved when new circumstances arise in the real-life operation of an AI solution. Through the “Data Observability” step, the data observability counterpart mechanism is triggered (on schedule or on-demand) to fully understand the health of the new data based on predefined data expectations, to discover potential distribution shifts, eliminate data downtime through automated monitoring, and triaging techniques to identify, evaluate and resolve potential

data quality and reliability issues. Similar to how data observability works, the “Model Observability” step allows data scientists to set appropriate baselines (based on findings from the “Model Training” or “Model Evaluation” steps), monitor the model’s health (i.e. model and feature drift detection, model performance, bias detected in (sub)groups defined by one or more sensitive attributes) and compare shifts to root cause performance degradation. To achieve this objective, it is again crucial to utilize models that make predictions with uncertainty, as an escalation in prediction uncertainty is a critical indicator of model deterioration caused by a distribution shift. In practice, Model Observability provides clear signals for the most opportune moments to retrain the AI models. To this direction, by adopting Adaptive AI techniques, deployed solutions can continuously learn based on new data at runtime and adapt more quickly to changes, as well as to resist or absorb disruptions.

B. AI-DAPT Technical Architecture

The functionality described in the AI-DAPT concept in the previous section will be delivered through a number of services (a) within the AI-DAPT integrated platform; and (b) within different AI technologies and data analytics platforms. In particular, the AI-DAPT Reference Architecture consists of a set of services conceptually divided in 7 layers (see Fig.2)

Fig. 2. AI-DAPT Technical Architecture

The Data Lifecycle Management Services practically refer to how data can be consistently collected and managed, through the configuration of appropriate data pipelines. The AI Lifecycle Management Services are responsible for managing the AI models and their associated pipelines. Such services entail the step-by-step, collaborative design, validation and handling of AI pipelines bringing together different data preparation, model engineering and explainability functionalities on the input data (i.e. the outcome of a corresponding data pipeline or of another AI pipeline) through the AI Pipeline Manager. The training, explanation generation, management, tracking and evaluation (both from performance and security perspectives) activities related to hybrid AI models are handled by the Hybrid AI Model Manager. The Data/AI Execution Services undertake the orchestration of the underlying engines that are spawn on-demand when a data/AI pipeline needs to be executed and invoke in a sequential manner a set of services, forwarding them the corresponding pipeline configuration. The Data-AI Insights Services provide the core human interaction interfaces with the business experts and data scientists for collaboration purposes and for gaining insights in different phases towards extracting data-driven intelligence. The Data-AI Pipeline Monitoring Services handle the real-life operation of data/AI pipelines that are deployed and run on schedule or on an event-based basis for an AI solution. Finally, the

Platform Management Services provides horizontal services across all service layers.

IV. DEMONSTRATION SCENARIOS AND CHALLENGES AHEAD

AI-DAPT will be tested and validated in real-life settings in 4 industrial demonstrators. Each demonstrator has at its centre a core domain (Health, Robotics, Energy and Manufacturing) to validate the applicability of the generic AI-DAPT solution in those verticals.

In the Health domain, the focus is on developing non-invasive devices for continuous glucose monitoring, crucial for diabetic patients. The project aims to utilize AI for analysing photoplethysmography (PPG) curves to accurately predict glucose levels [36]. This endeavour holds immense potential to revolutionize diabetes management by providing patients with easy-to-use, wearable devices that offer reliable glucose monitoring without the need for invasive procedures. AI-DAPT will concentrate on early detection and monitoring of type 2 diabetes (T2D) using a non-invasive method that can provide valuable data for patients, healthcare providers, and medical researchers, as well as insurance companies. Photoplethysmography (PPG) is an optical technique that measures changes in blood volume, which can be combined with Machine Learning algorithms to create an innovative and holistic approach for diabetes detection and management. Key challenges are associated with the proposed AI pipeline that would involve several steps, including data collection from PPG sensors, waveform pre-processing and cleaning, and AI algorithm analysis to predict glucose levels. This AI algorithm would be trained using a large dataset of PPG waveforms and corresponding glucose levels. Addressing data security and privacy concerns needs to be considered.

In Robotics, the project aims to enhance human-machine collaboration in manufacturing processes. The main challenge lies in effectively integrating real-time data on human behaviour with historical data. Here, AI will play a pivotal role in adapting automation systems to match the skills and experiences of human operators. By leveraging AI, manufacturing processes can become more flexible, responsive, and aligned with the capabilities and preferences of human workers. AI-DAPT focuses on cognitive ergonomics in a scenario of a human operator performing visual quality control with the support of a robot and 3D vision system. Data gathered will be processed through Data/AI pipeline targeting at inspiring the system to adapt to operators' skills and experience. This data pertains to the skills and experience profiles of the operators, enabling the system to adapt to the human background and potentially upskill it.

In the Energy domain, the project will focus on implementing demand response initiatives to improve energy efficiency in buildings. AI will be leveraged for demand forecasting and optimizing energy consumption based on various factors such as weather conditions and user preferences. By harnessing AI capabilities, energy suppliers and utilities can implement cost-effective measures to enhance energy efficiency while meeting the dynamic demands of consumers and the market. The demonstrator will take advantage of the AI-DAPT AIOps / intelligent pipeline lifecycle framework, covering the challenging task of intertwining relations of supply-side demand response techniques as well as the market-oriented load and price forecasting strategies in a layered approach addressing the business, legal/ethics, environmental, AI logic/models, data,

service, and system requirements of the pilot. In this respect, demand-side response analysis and forecasting will be enabled by ML techniques, which are trained on historical time-series data of energy consumption and other parameters, such as outdoor weather conditions, user comfort limits-schedules, and coupled with optimization algorithms.

Finally, in the Manufacturing sector, the project tackles the challenge of efficiently maintaining production equipment. AI will be utilized for forecasting, planning, and prediction to ensure timely maintenance and repair activities without disrupting production schedules. Synthetic data generation will be employed to effectively train AI algorithms, enabling them to accurately predict maintenance needs and optimize resource allocation. By integrating AI-driven predictive maintenance strategies, manufacturers can enhance equipment reliability, minimize downtime, and optimize production efficiency. However, challenges remain, including the need for trustworthy training data for unique events and new equipment types, as well as the adaptation of AI models in real-time to unforeseen defects or damage events, each requiring new model development.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The AI-DAPT project is a novel EU-funded project offering a holistic approach to harness the power of data and AI for solving complex real-world problems. Although still in its foundational stages, with much of the proposed framework and architecture yet to be fully realized, the innovative concept and technical architecture position the project to establish a new standard for integrating data-centric methodologies with AI pipelines. This paves the way for the development of more robust, reliable, and fair AI solutions.

With its phased approach spanning data design, sculpting, generation, model delivery, and data-model optimization, AI-DAPT provides a comprehensive framework for orchestrating intelligent data/AI pipelines. The project leverages advanced techniques such as synthetic data generation and hybrid science-guided ML, empowering organizations to tackle diverse challenges across various domains. From data lifecycle management to platform management, each layer of the technical architecture plays a crucial role in ensuring the efficiency, reliability, and scalability of AI solutions.

In the coming years, AI-DAPT faces significant challenges in demonstrating its effectiveness across diverse real-life scenarios in health, robotics, energy, and manufacturing. Key immediate priorities involve refining the presented framework through real-world feedback via co-creation workshops. Additionally, AI-DAPT will prioritize addressing ethical and societal implications by ensuring transparency, fairness, accountability, and privacy protection throughout its lifecycle, fostering responsible AI deployment through stakeholder engagement.

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